

Contextualising Research Projects

Facilitating Responsible Participation Special Interest Group,
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Contextualisation in research is a way to consider the influence of historical, social, cultural and technical contexts where knowledge is produced in relation to where it is received and used. This worksheet is designed to reflect on participation, access and facilitating collaboration in research projects.

Choose a research project that you are working on and get started with this worksheet! Compare your worksheets with other colleagues in the project.

Project Details:

Project title, affiliation, important links and stakeholders/actors (developers, collaborators, contributors, funders, users etc.) details.

Goals	Short-term goals	Long-term goals
Project goals		
Sustainable goals (social, global)		

Overlapping Interests	Researchers in the Project	Social actors affected by the project
Skills & lived experience		
Positive impact		
Negative impact		

Social, Cultural & Historical Context

in which this project takes place:

in which knowledge produced from this project is received:

Different Forms of Participation

Ensuring participation of all actors in research and resource management through project design, implementation and uptake processes.

Equitable collaboration and communication plans with all stakeholders

Ensuring effective collaboration and communication process to avoid possible exclusion of all stakeholders including informal and local groups. Here you can also provide details on how you will seek support to sustain your participation and in what ways you might be able to help/support others.

Tools, Resources & Inclusive Infrastructure

Promoting interactions between data providers and data users, and enable them to produce, gather, share, collaborate, and use scientific knowledge.